

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING WRESTLING TO STUDENTS

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Annotation: This article discusses modern methods of effectively teaching students the sport of wrestling. Traditional and innovative approaches are analyzed, and the results of using ICT, visual and interactive methods in the teaching process are considered. The impact of methodological approaches is also assessed based on empirical data.

Introduction: Kurash is a sport that has a national identity within the sphere of physical education and sports, playing an important role in the formation of physical and mental potential in young people. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is making separate decisions on the international promotion of kurash. Therefore, teaching it to the younger generation, especially high-quality teaching using modern methods in universities, remains an urgent issue.

While traditional lessons used more passive methods based on teacher instructions, interactive and technological methods that involve students as active participants are now becoming effective. This article will analyze these modern methodological approaches in depth.

Research methodology

The following methods were used in the study:

- Experimental approach – a controlled and experimental study was conducted on two groups of students.
- Questionnaire – opinions on modern methods were collected among students and teachers.

- Observation and video analysis – the training process was analyzed.

Participants

40 students studying at the 2nd level of Tashkent State University of Physical Education and Sports participated. They were divided into two groups: experimental group and control group.

Teaching methods

- Experimental group: interactive lessons, video analysis, smart simulators, demonstration of movements using a drone, reflective discussion.
- Control group: traditional method – teacher demonstration, oral explanation, classic wrestling exercises.

RESULTS

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The experimental group achieved the following changes:

Indicator Initial (%) 2 days (%)

Mu 65 85

Adaptability 70 90

Technician each 60 88

The changes in the control group were smaller (10–15%).

Survey results

- 92% of students recognized that interactive approaches increased motivation.
- 88% of students stated that technological tools (video, graphics, QR-tests) made lessons more interesting.
- Teachers recognized that modern methods require more preparation, but confirmed that the results are high.

DISCUSSION

The results show that modern methods (visual, reflective, ICT-based) in teaching wrestling are highly effective. In particular, visual analysis (video recordings), interactive discussion and an individual approach increase student learning.

In addition, technological tools (mobile applications, VR simulators, filming wrestling movements with a drone) encourage students to analyze their own activities, which leads to a deeper understanding of wrestling techniques.

Also, analysis using sensor equipment in teaching safety and balance in wrestling significantly increases the quality of the lesson. However, modern methods require high technical literacy from the teacher.

CONCLUSION

The use of modern methods in teaching wrestling:

- Attracts students to the lesson,
- Facilitates the mastery of techniques and tactics,
- Increases interest in sports.

In teaching wrestling in higher education institutions, it is necessary to combine traditional methods with innovative approaches.

- Use of VR simulators and mobile applications in wrestling training.
- Introduction of ICT training courses for teachers.
- Formation of individual athlete portfolios based on visual analysis (video surveillance).

References

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